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Performance Analysis and Optimization of Distributed Hybrid Active-Passive RIS-Aided THz Wireless Systems

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Background (1): Terahertz (THz) Communications

The electromagnetic spectrum^[1]

- ❑ Plays key roles for 6G for 2030 and Beyond
- ❑ Accommodates massive connectivity
- ❑ Features Tbit/s data-rate
- ❑ Suffers from **high pathloss** and **severe blockage**

Pathloss in THz communication^[2]

[1] Rohde & Schwarz's white paper: *Fundamentals of THz technology for 6G*, Aug. 2022.

[2] Z. Chen, B. Ning, C. Han, Z. Tian and S. Li, "Intelligent Reflecting Surface Assisted Terahertz Communications Toward 6G," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol.

Background (2): Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS)

Architecture of RIS/IRS^[3]

Passive RIS element based on PIN diode^[3]

Passive vs. Active RIS^[4]

- ❑ Consist of an array of low-cost elements
- ❑ Achieve **improved SNR** at a receiver
- ❑ Create **virtual LoS links** to deal with blockage

[3] Q. Wu et al., "Intelligent Reflecting Surface-Aided Wireless Communications: A Tutorial," *IEEE TCom*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 3313-3351, May 2021

[4] Z. Zhang et al., "Active RIS vs. Passive RIS: Which Will Prevail in 6G?," *IEEE TWC*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 1707-1725, Mar. 2023

Background (3): RIS-aided THz Systems

Research focus:

Hardware design of RIS for THz bands

RIS-THz channel estimation and characterization

Performance analysis and beamforming optimization

Applications of THz-IRS communications^[2]

- a) high-speed fronthaul/backhaul; b) cellular connected UAVs; c) wireless data center;
d) enhanced indoor coverage; e) vehicular communication; f) physical layer security

[2] Z. Chen, B. Ning, C. Han, Z. Tian and S. Li, "Intelligent Reflecting Surface Assisted Terahertz Communications Toward 6G," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 110-117, Dec. 2021

Motivation: Distributed Hybrid RIS-Aided THz Systems

Proposed System (1): System Model

□ The equivalent e2e channel from the AP to the user

$$y = \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} h_{1,m} a_{l,m} e^{j\theta_{l,m}} g_{l,m},$$

□ The superimposed signal received by the user

Hardware Impairment

$$\phi \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \kappa^2 P_0)$$

Active RIS noise

$$z_{l,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_z)$$

$$r = \underbrace{y(\sqrt{P_0}s + \phi)}_{\text{Signal transmission via reflected link}} + \underbrace{\sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} a_{l,m} e^{j\theta_{l,m}} g_{l,m} z_{l,m}}_{\text{Noise introduced by active RISs}} + \underbrace{n}_{\text{Noise introduced at user}},$$

□ The received signal-to-distortion-plus-noise ratio

$$\gamma = \frac{\bar{\gamma}|y|^2}{\kappa^2 \bar{\gamma}|y|^2 + \xi Z + 1}$$

where $\bar{\gamma} \triangleq P_0/N_0$, $\xi \triangleq N_z/N_0$, and $Z \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} a_{l,m}^2 |g_{l,m}|^2$

AWGN noise

$$n \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_0)$$

Proposed System (2): Phase-Shift and Consumed Power

Phase-shift adjustments

- **Continuous phase adjustment**: optimal phase-shift (i.e., no errors)
- **Discrete phase-shift (B bits)**: quantization errors follow a uniform distribution

Power consumption model

Power consumption of passive RIS elements

Power consumption of active RIS elements

$$P_{H-RIS,l} = P_{pRIS,l} + P_{aRIS,l}$$

$$P_{pRIS,l} = M_{p,l} P_{c,r}$$

$$P_{aRIS,l} = p_{out} / \eta_1 + M_{a,l} (P_{c,r} + P_{dc})$$

$$p_{out} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} a_{i,m}^2 (P_0 |h_{i,m}|^2 + N_z)$$

Proposed System (3): THz Channel Model

- THz channel model consists of the path gain and small-scale fading, i.e.,

$$h = \bar{h} \tilde{h}$$

- The THz path gain is due to propagation gain and molecular absorption gain, i.e.,

$$\bar{h} = \frac{c\sqrt{G_t G_r}}{4\pi f d} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \rho(f) d}$$

Molecular absorption coefficient

- The α - μ small-scale fading distribution for THz transmissions with CDF and PDF are

$$f_{|\tilde{h}|}(x) = \frac{\alpha \beta^{\alpha \mu}}{\Omega^{\alpha \mu} \Gamma(\mu)} x^{\alpha \mu - 1} e^{-(\beta \frac{x}{\Omega})^{\alpha}}$$

$$F_{|\tilde{h}|}(x) = \frac{\gamma(\mu, (\beta \frac{x}{\Omega})^{\alpha})}{\Gamma(\mu)}$$

- Special cases: Gamma ($\alpha = 1$), exponential ($\alpha = 1$; $\mu = 1$), Weibull ($\alpha = 1$), Nakagami- m ($\alpha = 2$; $\mu = m$), Rayleigh ($\alpha = 2$; $\mu = 1$), and one-sided Gaussian distributions ($\alpha = 2$; $\mu = 1/2$)

Analysis (1): Distributions of The e2e Channel

□ Adopt **Lyapunov central limit theorem (CLT)** to approximate the channel distribution

Fig. 2. PDF and CDF of $|y|^2$.

Theorem 1: The e2e channel $|y|^2$ associated with the optimal RIS phase-shifts can be approximated as a Gamma random variable, i.e.,

$$|y|^2 \stackrel{M \rightarrow \infty}{\sim} \text{Gamma}(u_o, v_o),$$

where the shape and the rate are given as $u_o = \frac{(\omega^2 + \Delta^2)^2}{2\Delta^4 + 4\Delta^2\omega^2}$ and $v_o = \frac{\omega^2 + \Delta^2}{2\Delta^4 + 4\Delta^2\omega^2}$, respectively. Also, we have $\omega \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} \omega_{l,m}$, $\Delta^2 \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} \Delta_{l,m}^2$, $\omega_{l,m} = \rho_{l,m} \mathbb{E}\{|h_{l,m}| |\tilde{g}_{l,m}|\} = \rho_{l,m} \Omega_{1,l} \Omega_{2,l}$, and $\Delta_{l,m}^2 = \rho_{l,m}^2 \Omega_{1,l}^2 \Omega_{2,l}^2 \left[\prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{\Gamma(\mu_{i,l}) \Gamma(\mu_{i,l} + 2/\alpha_{i,l})}{\Gamma^2(\mu_{i,l} + 1/\alpha_{i,l})} - 1 \right]$.

Corollary 1: The e2e channel $|y|^2$ associated with the RIS discrete phase-shifts can be approximated as a Gamma random variable, i.e.,

$$|y|^2 \stackrel{M \rightarrow \infty}{\sim} \text{Gamma}(u_e, v_e),$$

where $u_e \triangleq \aleph^2 / \Xi^2$ and $v_e \triangleq \aleph / \Xi^2$ are the shape and the rate, respectively. Also, we have $\aleph \triangleq \omega_U^2 + \Delta_U^2 + \Delta_V^2$, $\Xi \triangleq 4\Delta_U^2 \omega_U^2 + 2\Delta_U^4 + 2\Delta_V^4$, $\omega_U \triangleq \frac{\sin \delta}{\delta} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} \omega_{l,m}$, $\Delta_U^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\sin 2\delta}{2\delta} \right) \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} \Delta_{l,m}^2$, and $\Delta_V^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sin 2\delta}{2\delta} \right) \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m=1}^{M_l} \Delta_{l,m}^2$.

- Approximate as a gamma random variable by using moment matching

Fig. 3. PDF and CDF of Z .

Corollary 2: The term Z defined in (8) can be approximated as a Gamma random variable, i.e.,

$$Z \sim \text{Gamma}(u_z, v_z),$$

where $u_z = \omega_z^2 / \Delta_z^2$ and $v_z = \omega_z / \Delta_z^2$ are the shape and the rate, respectively. Moreover, we have

$$\omega_z = \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} \omega_{l,m}^z, \quad \Delta_z^2 = \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} \Delta_{l,m}^z,$$

$$\omega_{l,m}^z \triangleq \tau_{l,m} \Omega_{2,l}^2 \frac{\Gamma(\mu_{2,l}) \Gamma(\mu_{2,l} + 2/\alpha_{2,l})}{\Gamma^2(\mu_{2,l} + 1/\alpha_{2,l})}, \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_{l,m}^z \triangleq \tau_{l,m}^2 \Omega_{2,l}^4 \frac{\Gamma^2(\mu_{2,l})}{\Gamma^4(\mu_{2,l} + 1/\alpha_{2,l})} \left[\Gamma(\mu_{2,l}) \Gamma\left(\mu_{2,l} + \frac{4}{\alpha_{2,l}}\right) - \Gamma^2\left(\mu_{2,l} + \frac{2}{\alpha_{2,l}}\right) \right].$$

$$Z \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_{a,l}} a_{l,m}^2 |g_{l,m}|^2$$

Analysis (3): The Scaling Law of The Received SNR

□ Asymptotic received SNR vs. the numbers of active/passive RIS elements

Theorem 2: The asymptotic SNR in the H-RIS-aided system with no HWI is simultaneously **proportional to the number of active RIS elements M_a and the squared number of passive RIS elements M_p^2** . Also, in the presence of HWI, the asymptotic SNR $\gamma \xrightarrow{M_a, M_p \rightarrow \infty} 1/\kappa^2$.

Theorem 3: The SNR loss when using the discrete phase-shifts with B bits compared to the optimal continuous phase-shifts at the large M regime is given as

$$\varrho(B) = \begin{cases} \text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2^B}\right) & , \kappa^2 = 0 \\ 1 & , \kappa^2 \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

$$P_{out} = Pr(\gamma < \gamma_{th})$$

□ Expression of OP

$$P_{out} = \begin{cases} \frac{\gamma(u, Q_2)}{\Gamma(u)} + \frac{e^{-Q_2}}{\Gamma(u)\Gamma(u_z)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u-1}{k} \frac{Q_1^{k+1} Q_2^{u-1-k} \Gamma(u_z+1+k)}{(k+1)(Q_1+1)^{u_z+1+k}} \\ \times {}_2F_1\left(1, u_z+1+k; k+2; \frac{Q_1}{Q_1+1}\right), & \text{if } \gamma_{th} < 1/\kappa^2 \\ 1, & \text{if } \gamma_{th} \geq 1/\kappa^2, \end{cases}$$

where $Q_1 \triangleq \frac{\gamma_{th} v \xi}{\bar{\gamma}(1-\kappa^2\gamma_{th})v_z}$, $Q_2 \triangleq \frac{\gamma_{th} v}{\bar{\gamma}(1-\kappa^2\gamma_{th})}$, and ${}_2F_1(\cdot)$ denotes the hypergeometric function [46].

□ High SNR asymptotic

$$P_{out}^{\infty} \approx \left(\frac{\gamma_{th} v}{\bar{\gamma}(1-\kappa^2\gamma_{th})} \right)^u \frac{1}{\Gamma(u+1)\Gamma(u_z)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u}{k} \left(\frac{\xi}{v_z} \right)^k \times \Gamma(u_z+k).$$

The active RIS noise and/or the hardware impairments do not affect the diversity order of the OP

Expressions of Ergodic capacity

$$C_{e, \kappa^2 \neq 0} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(u)\Gamma(u_z) \ln 2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u}{k} \left(\frac{\xi}{v_z}\right)^k \times$$

$$\left[G_{1,0:2,2:1,1}^{1,0:1,2:1,1} \left(u \mid 1 - u_z - k \mid 1, 1 \mid \frac{(1 + \kappa^2)\bar{\gamma}}{v}, \frac{\xi}{v_z} \right) \right.$$

$$\left. - G_{1,0:2,2:1,1}^{1,0:1,2:1,1} \left(u \mid 1 - u_z - k \mid 1, 1 \mid \frac{\kappa^2 \bar{\gamma}}{v}, \frac{\xi}{v_z} \right) \right],$$

$$C_{e, \kappa^2 = 0} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(u)\Gamma(u_z) \ln 2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u}{k} \left(\frac{\xi}{v_z}\right)^k \times$$

$$G_{1,0:2,2:1,1}^{1,0:1,2:1,1} \left(u \mid 1 - u_z - k \mid 1, 1 \mid \frac{\bar{\gamma}}{v}, \frac{\xi}{v_z} \right),$$

where G(.) denotes the extended generalized bivariate Meijer-G function

High SNR asymptotic

$$C_e^\infty = \begin{cases} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{\kappa^2} \right) \frac{1}{\Gamma(u_z)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u}{k} \left(\frac{\xi}{v_z}\right)^k \Gamma(u_z + k), & \text{if } \kappa^2 \neq 0 \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma(u_z)} \left[\log_2(\bar{\gamma}) + \log_2 \frac{e^{\psi(u)}}{v} \right] \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{u}{k} \left(\frac{\xi}{v_z}\right)^k \Gamma(u_z + k) & \text{if } \kappa^2 = 0. \end{cases}$$

With HWI: capacity tends to be saturated

No HWI: capacity increases logarithmically with the SNR

Optimization: Energy Efficiency Maximization

❑ **Energy efficiency**: measured based on the ergodic capacity and the average power consumption

❑ **EE maximization problem**:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{P_0} EE(P_0) = \frac{W_B C_e(P_0)}{I_1 P_0 + I_2} \\ & \text{subject to } 0 \leq P_0 \leq P_{0,max} \\ & Pr(\gamma < \gamma_{th}) < \epsilon, \end{aligned}$$

Bandwidth

Ergodic capacity

I_1 and I_2 are coefficients

Maximum transmit power

SNR constraint

❑ The objective function $EE(P_0)$ is **quasi-concave** w.r.t. P_0

❑ Use **golden-section search** to find the optimal transmit power

Simulation Results (1): System Setup and Parameters

SIMULATION PARAMETERS.

Parameters	Values
Operating frequency	300 (GHz) [18], [19]
Transmission bandwidth	10 (GHz) [18], [19]
Molecular absorption coefficient	$\rho = 3.18 \times 10^{-4}$ per meter [18], [19]
Efficiency of power amplifiers	$\eta = \eta_1 = 0.83$ [19], [43]
Circuit power consumption	$P_{c,a} = P_{c,r} = P_{c,u} = 10$ (dBm) [26], [43]
Hardware impairment level	$\kappa^2 = 0.08$ [19]
Antenna gains	$G_t = 50, G_r = 20$ (dBi) [20]
SNR threshold	$\gamma_{th} = 6$ (dB) [18]
Number of distributed RIS panels	$L = 3$ [39]
Discrete phase-shifts	$B = 2$ (bits) [45]
Amplification gain of all active RIS	$a = 6$ (dB) [27]
Noise power	$N_0 = N_z = -74$ (dBm) [18], [19]

Simulation Results (2): Outage Probability

- Outage probability (OP) vs. transmit power

OP becomes lower when the transmit power is higher, and/or the HWI level is smaller

Simulation Results (3): Ergodic Capacity

- Ergodic capacity vs. transmit power

Capacity will be saturated at the high SNR region when there presents the HWI

Simulation Results (4): Energy Efficiency (EE)

- Energy efficiency vs. transmit power ($\varepsilon = 0.01$)

At high power region, the effects of HWI become more serious

Simulation Results (5): Maximum EE

- Maximum EE vs. number of active RIS elements ($P_{0,\max} = 10 \text{ W}$, $M_l = 70$)

Hybrid RIS scheme can achieve higher EE than the fully passive and fully active RIS schemes

- Proposed a distributed hybrid active-passive RIS-assisted THz system in the presence of hardware impairments and α - μ small-scale fading channels
- Characterized the e2e channel by gamma distribution approximation to facilitate the OP and capacity analysis
- Analyzed the scaling law of the received SNR
- Evaluated impacts of hardware impairments, numbers of active and passive RIS elements, and phase quantization errors
- Optimized transmit power for the maximum EE: hybrid RIS scheme achieves higher EE than its counterparts

Thank You